

Economic Evaluation of Solar Water Collectors on Building Walls in Israel

Residential Buildings in Tel Aviv

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Version 1.1.1, 18 February 2026

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.18678230

all versions DOI:10.5281/zenodo.18678229

Abstract

In Israel, 85% of homes have solar water heaters (SWH), according to legislation from 1980 that required the installation of SWH on the top 9 floors of new residential buildings. Building heights are steadily increasing, and more housing units are left without SWH.

The solar energy legislation was repealed in 2025, leaving room on the roof for 15 kVA photovoltaic panels.

For the Israeli population, SWH is not only the most economical way to heat sanitary water, but also a symbol of a standard of living and a very convenient way to supply hot water.

The national standard requires the installation of solar collectors at a tilt angle of 45° facing south. All other tilt angles and collector orientations require an increase in collector size.

This work is related to the tilt angle of 90° in all directions. The analysis includes calculations of the collector size, energy and water temperature that can be provided by collectors installed on the external walls of the buildings. The best location to install solar collectors is the lower wall of the balcony, separately for each apartment. The collectors are located in different directions of the building and their performance was analyzed for every 22.5 degrees, resulting in 16 cases.

In the first and second options, five cases of building orientation were rejected due to low solar gain, the other 11 cases show reasonable results. The highest solar gain in winter is on the south wall, and throughout the year on the east-south wall.

Option 3 includes all possible directions of the building walls, but increases the winter electricity backup for cases rejected in option 2.

All cases of Option 2 and Option 3 are very profitable.

The average collector size in Option 3 is 3.26 m², a maximum of 3.58 m² in the case of SWW+WNN and a minimum of 2.81 m² for the south wall. The average electricity saving is 1,427 kWh/y for an apartment with 150 liter SWH.

The average PV/I value in Option 3 is 5.38, a maximum of 6.91 for the south wall, and a minimum of 3.84 for the WN+NE case.

The sensitivity analysis shows that even after reducing the life expectancy of the SWH from 20 years to 8 years, all cases remain very profitable with an average PV/I value of 2.91 and a minimum of 2.08.

Glossary

$\Delta\%$	change in collector size in %, wherever applicable
Δt	temperature difference, °C
\$	USD - currency
Ave	average
CF	Conversion Factor between Solar Radiation on Building Wall and Solar Radiation on Horizontal Surface
CRF	Capital Recovery Factor [10]
IMS	Israel Meteorological Service website [1] [2]
NG	Nowagreen website [4]
NPV	Net Present Value = Present Value – Net Investment, \$
O-M	Open-Meteo website [3]
PV	in context of economic evaluation, PV=Present Value of future savings. $PV = \text{Annual saving}/CRF$ [\$]
PV	in context of solar energy, PV is Photo-Voltaic solar cell panel
SE	global solar radiation [W/m ²]
SWH	Solar Water Heater
Ref	reference

Units

This work is in metric units (SI system). Hot water energy is also calculated in kilocalories (kcal) as the most convenient unit for thermal calculations involving hot water, while 1 kcal is the energy required to heat 1 liter of water by 1 Centigrade. Currency is USD. USD to ILS exchange rate is 3.086 as of 4 Feb 2026. All prices include VAT.

The time is GMT+2hr, DST (summer time) is not considered.

The Building and the Apartment

The typical multi-apartment building in Israel has 4 apartments on each floor. Each apartment is located at the corner of the building with two outside walls facing two different directions.

Solar radiation will be calculated on both walls, selecting the wall with better results in December and January. The analysis will be for walls in 16 directions at every 22.5 degrees.

Solar water collectors require a drainage system. Installing the solar collectors on the balcony wall (or on the service balcony) will save this additional cost and allow much easier replacement of the leaking collector. This is also the best location to install the storage tank, with the shortest circulation piping between the collector and the storage tank. The collector should be located as low as possible (close to the floor) and the storage tank as high as possible (close to the ceiling).

The current work applies a vertical storage tank that is more efficient than a horizontal storage tank. In the case of a horizontal storage tank, the size of the collector should be increased by at least 10%.

Solar Radiation Data Sources

Global solar radiation in Israel can be found on the Meteorological Service (IMS) website [1].

The site includes 10 minutes datasets of global solar radiation on horizontal surface for various locations and periods [1], and hourly data for a typical year based on the years 1991-2005 [2].

The datasets from the Meteorological Service (IMS) [1] [2] are for Bet Dagan near Tel Aviv at coordinates @32.007,34.813.

Global solar radiation data can also be found on the Open-Meteo (O-M) website [3].

The records are for every hour and every day. The location selected for this work is @32.0211,34.8492 near Bet Dagan. The downloaded datasets from this site are for the years 2023 and 2024 [3].

Table 1 - Global solar radiation data sources [1] [2] [3]

Set #	Dataset	Source	Ref	frequency of records	period
1	IMS Typical year	IMS	[2]	1 hour	typical year
2	IMS 2023	IMS	[1]	10 min	2023
3	IMS 2024	IMS	[1]	10 min	2024
4	O-M 2023	O-M	[3]	1 hour	2023
5	O-M 2024	O-M	[3]	1 hour	2024

Table 2 - Global solar radiation on horizontal surface kWh/year,m2, and Wh/day,m2 in January and December [1] [2] [3]

SE Set #	Dataset	SE kWh/y,m2	Jan: Wh/day,m2	Dec: Wh/day,m2
1	IMS Typical year	1,874	2,811	2,565
2	IMS 2023	1,985	3,191	2,922
3	IMS 2024	2,038	2,768	3,054
4	O-M 2023	1,944	3,119	2,938
5	O-M 2024	1,966	2,798	3,036

Set #1 – IMS Typical year [2] was selected for further calculations, as this set is most conservative among all sets.

Conversion Factors between Solar Radiation on the Building Wall and Solar Radiation on Horizontal Surface

The following sources of information were considered in this work for the Conversion Factor (CF):

- Dataset: Hourly Solar Radiation at Tilt Angle and Direction in Tel Aviv (NG) [4]
- Open-Meteo (O-M) internet site: global solar radiation at any tilt angle and any direction (azimuth) [3]
- Israeli Standard: SI 579 - Solar water heating systems – 1995 (SI) [5]

Conversion factors dataset for Tel Aviv is on the website: "*Hourly Solar Radiation at Tilt Angle and Direction in Tel Aviv*" (Nowagreen – NG) [4].

In addition, the Open-Meteo (O-M) database [3] includes global solar radiation at every tilt angle and in every direction (azimuth), and is used in this work to determine the conversion factors between the radiation on the building walls and the global solar radiation on a horizontal surface in Tel Aviv.

The Israeli standard for solar heaters SI579 [5] contains a table of the required increase in collector area depending on the tilt angle and azimuth.

Table 3 - Conversion Factor (CF) data sources [3] [4] [5]

CF Set #	Source	Ref	details	Step
1	NG	[4]	every hour, every month	22.5 deg
2	O-M	[3]	every hour, every month	22.5 deg
3	SI	[5]	yearly total	10 deg

Table 4 - Conversion Factors (CF) according to the Israeli Standard [5]

Degrees from South	Orientation	Conversion Factor CF	Collector Size x
0.0	S	0.500	2.0
22.5	ESS, SSW	0.556	1.8
45.0	ES, SW	0.667	1.5
67.5	EES, SWW	0.625	1.6
90.0	E, W	0.526	1.9

Global Solar Radiation on Building Walls

The global solar radiation on the walls of the building is calculated by multiplying the global solar radiation on a horizontal surface by the relevant CF conversion factor for the wall direction.

Table 5 - Solar radiation on building walls datasets

Set #	SE set #	CF Set #
11	1	1 NG [4]
12	1	2 O-M [3]
13	1	3 SI [5]

Table 6 - Solar radiation on building walls in 16 directions, kWh/year,m2

Set #	N	WNN	WN	WWN	W	SWW	SW	SSW	S	ESS	ES	EES	E	NEE	NE	NNE
11	732	808	911	1,023	1,129	1,216	1,264	1,282	1,284	1,290	1,269	1,223	1,129	1,001	882	771
12	511	566	692	841	977	1,078	1,133	1,153	1,164	1,205	1,219	1,176	1,069	913	737	585
13					987	1,172	1,250	1,041	937	1,041	1,250	1,172	987			

Table 7 - Solar radiation on building walls in 16 directions in January, Wh/day,m2

Set #	N	WNN	WN	WWN	W	SWW	SW	SSW	S	ESS	ES	EES	E	NEE	NE	NNE
11	979	1185	1349	1552	1819	2168	2592	3102	3496	3500	3129	2524	1819	1212	815	783
12	776	776	831	1087	1493	1954	2439	2879	3060	2893	2458	1978	1511	1096	836	776

Table 8 - Solar radiation on building walls in 16 directions in December, Wh/day,m2

Set #	N	WNN	WN	WWN	W	SWW	SW	SSW	S	ESS	ES	EES	E	NEE	NE	NNE
11	847	1023	1175	1280	1580	2222	2882	3432	3568	3286	2663	2124	1580	1145	900	843
12	704	704	733	981	1423	2021	2686	3391	3778	3697	3190	2527	1823	1214	795	704

Set #13 was discarded because it does not have data for 7 directions, January and December.

Set #12 was selected as it is more conservative than Set #11 for all directions for total annual solar radiation.

Set #12 includes MSI solar radiation data on horizontal surface for a typical year based on the years 1991-2005 [2] and conversion factors CF based on the Open-Meteo (O-M) database [3], which includes global solar radiation at any tilt angle and any direction (azimuth),

Table 9 - Solar global radiation on building walls in 16 direction – the selected Set #12, Wh/day,m2

month	N	WNN	WN	WWN	W	SWW	SW	SSW	S	ESS	ES	EES	E	NEE	NE	NNE
1	776	776	831	1,087	1,493	1,954	2,439	2,879	3,060	2,893	2,458	1,978	1,511	1,096	836	776
2	1,063	1,067	1,187	1,484	1,871	2,279	2,667	3,020	3,193	3,051	2,723	2,338	1,913	1,502	1,190	1,067
3	1,377	1,433	1,743	2,217	2,722	3,142	3,424	3,584	3,660	3,519	3,314	3,035	2,661	2,213	1,766	1,452
4	1,639	1,835	2,256	2,693	3,036	3,230	3,233	3,116	3,015	3,129	3,272	3,275	3,096	2,759	2,302	1,867
5	2,001	2,301	2,821	3,248	3,452	3,437	3,185	2,771	2,484	2,830	3,316	3,633	3,669	3,453	2,998	2,408
6	2,210	2,563	3,224	3,696	3,857	3,698	3,267	2,602	2,178	2,618	3,359	3,889	4,079	3,915	3,447	2,716
7	1,931	2,302	2,936	3,416	3,613	3,500	3,136	2,548	2,142	2,514	3,115	3,536	3,656	3,459	3,017	2,370
8	1,732	2,087	2,730	3,296	3,660	3,754	3,572	3,199	2,916	3,251	3,695	3,916	3,840	3,467	2,861	2,174
9	1,318	1,471	1,899	2,415	2,871	3,199	3,345	3,376	3,457	3,641	3,770	3,702	3,379	2,850	2,192	1,595
10	1,183	1,209	1,455	1,934	2,526	3,112	3,632	4,115	4,564	4,588	4,318	3,845	3,195	2,437	1,715	1,248
11	839	839	892	1,133	1,534	2,058	2,629	3,292	3,799	3,856	3,505	2,946	2,270	1,605	1,057	839
12	704	704	733	981	1,423	2,021	2,686	3,391	3,778	3,697	3,190	2,527	1,823	1,214	795	704

Chart 1 - Solar global radiation on South, East, and North walls – the selected Set #12, Wh/day,m2 [2] [3]

Cases Excluded from the Analysis for Option 1 and Option 2

As mentioned before, every apartment is located at the building corner with each wall facing another direction.

Table 10 - Walls directions and solar global radiation on the wall with higher radiation in January and December, Wh/day,m2

Wall 1	Wall 2	Jan	Dec	Excluded
N	E	1511	1823	x
NNE	EES	2893	3697	
NE	ES	2458	3190	
NEE	ESS	2893	3697	
E	S	3060	3778	
EES	SSW	2879	3391	
ES	SW	2458	3190	
ESS	SWW	2893	3697	
S	W	3060	3778	
SSW	WWN	2879	3391	
SW	WN	2439	2686	
SWW	WNN	1954	2021	
W	N	1493	1423	x
WWN	NNE	1087	981	x
WN	NE	836	795	x
WNN	NEE	1096	1214	x

Yellow background indicates the wall with higher solar radiation.
 Blue background indicates wall directions that receive too low solar radiation in January and December, therefore excluded from Option 1 and Option2.

Chart 2 - Walls directions and solar global radiation on the wall with higher radiation in January, Wh/day,m2

5 cases out of 16 (31%) of the wall directions are excluded from Option 1 and Option 2 due to the low solar radiation in January and December on both walls of the apartment.

Minimum Solar Radiation on the Wall

Five cases were excluded from the analysis due to the low solar radiation. Among the 11 cases included in the analysis, the lowest solar radiation is in the SWW+WNN case, where the solar radiation on the SWW wall is 1954 Wh/day,m² in January.

Table 11 - Minimum solar radiation on the wall for the SWW+WNN case in January

Minimum solar radiation [2] [6]	1,954	Wh/day,m ²
kcal/Whr	0.860	
Minimum solar radiation	1,680	kcal/day,m ²

Solar Water Heater

The solar water heater (SWH) analyzed in this work is a thermosyphonic system. Solar legislation in Israel distinguishes between vertical and horizontal storage tanks [5] [6].

In this work, a vertical storage tank is considered.

The system may include one collector or a few collectors; in both cases, this work defines the collector(s) array as a "collector".

Solar legislation in Israel required the installation of solar water heaters in new residential buildings on the upper 9 floors. Thermosyphonic systems are usually installed up to 4 floors from the roof.

The size of the solar collector is expressed in kcal/day for standard conditions, and not in m².

Requirements of the solar regulation:

- the size of the storage tank depends on the size of the residential unit, for a 4-room apartment (~100m²) it is 150 liters
- solar collector standard size is 41 kcal/d for each liter of the storage tank for thermosyphonic systems with a vertical storage tank if the collector is at 45° tilt angle facing south
- for all other tilt angles and directions, the collector size should be increased according to the national standard [6]
- the collector standard size is determined for the standard solar radiation of 4,400 kcal/day,m²

Formula 1 - Standard size of solar collector for a 4-room apartment

$$Q_s = 41 \text{ kcal/d,l} * 150 \text{ liter} = 6,150 \text{ kcal/day}$$

The 41 kcal/d,l requirement of the regulations is for the 45° collector's tilt angle facing south. All other conditions require an increase in the collector size.

The average solar radiation on the 45° tilt collector facing south in Tel Aviv is 3,304 kcal/day,m² in December, and 3,390 kcal/day,m² in January [2] [4].

The typical efficiency of the collector made in Israel is 60% [6].

Formula 2 - Hot water temperature in storage tank, °C

$$T_w = t_a + SE_{wall} * (1 + \Delta\%) * A * \eta / (V * cp_w * \rho_w)$$

$$T_w = t_a + SE_{wall} * (1 + \Delta\%) * A * \eta / V$$

T_w	hot water temperature in the storage tank, °C
t_a	city water, cold water temperature entering storage tank, °C
SE_{wall}	solar radiation on selected wall, kcal/day,m ²
$\Delta\%$	change in collector size in %, wherever applicable
A	collector area, m ²
η	average efficiency of the applied solar water collector
V	SWH storage tank volume, liter (L)
cp_w	specific heat of water = 1 kcal/kg,°C
ρ_w	water density = 1 kg/liter

Table 12 - Selected Solar Water Heater [8]

storage tank volume	150	liter
storage tank vertical/horizontal	vertical	
SWH cost including installation	1,523	\$
solar collector standard size	41	kcal/d,liter
solar collector standard size	6,150	kcal/d
standard solar radiation	4,400	kcal/day,m ²
solar collector standard efficiency	60%	
solar collector standard size	2.33	m ²
solar collector model	CR12B	
collector size	7,005	kcal/day
collector size	2.55	m ²
collector efficiency	62.4%	
collector cost	677	\$
collector cost	0.097	\$/kcal,d
collector cost	266	\$/m ²
warranty	4+4	years

The maximum solar collector size is required for the SWW wall of the SWW+WNN case.

Table 13 - Solar collector size for wall SWW

minimum solar radiation on tilt angle 45° facing South	3,304	kcal/day,m2
minimum solar radiation on wall SWW	1,680	kcal/day,m2
required increase of standard solar collector	97%	
solar collector standard size	6,150	kcal/day
required standard size of solar collector on wall SWW	12,095	kcal/day
selected collector CR12B	7,005	kcal/day
selected collector CR12B	2.55	m2
required increase of collector size	5,090	kcal/day
cost of the additional collector area	492	\$
required increase of collector area	73%	
required increase of collector area	1.85	m2
collector CR12B area for wall SWW	4.40	m2

The maximum solar collector size in Option 1 is 4.40 m2 for the SWW+WNN case. All other 10 accepted cases will require a smaller collector.

Input Data for the Economic Evaluation

Table 14 - Input data for economic evaluation for 150 liter SWH and alternative solution of 150 liter electric water heater [\$=USD]

standard SWH investment cost including installation	\$	1,523
electric water heater 150 L cost including installation	\$	1,066
cost of addition to the collector size	\$/kcal/d	0.11
cost of addition to the collector size	\$/m2	266
additional collector area	m2	0.00
additional collector area cost	\$	0
net investment cost	\$	457
electricity tariffs	\$/kWh	0.21
SWH energy available from SE [9]	kWh/y	2,076
SWH SE not used [9]	kWh/y	556
SWH SE used [9]	kWh/y	1,520
electricity saving of standard SWH	kWh/y	1,520
electricity saving of standard SWH	\$/y	317
life expectancy	years	20
Rate of Interest	%/y	6%
CRF [10]		0.0872
PV standard SWH	\$	3,634
PV/I standard SWH		7.95
max SWH cost (for PV/I=1.3)	\$	3,861

PV	Present Value of future savings $PV = \text{annual saving} / \text{CRF}$
SWH	Solar Water Heater 150 liter
SE	Solar Energy
CRF	Capital Recovery Factor
NPV	Net Present Value = $PV - I$

PV/I Present Value of future savings to net investment
 max SWH cost theoretical SWH cost that would result in $PV/I=1.3$, 30% profit during the life expectancy of SWH

Net investment is calculated as the cost of SWH including installation, reduced by the cost of the alternative to SWH including installation.

The cheapest alternative to the SWH is an electric water heater of 150 liters including installation.

Components of the SWH cost:

- Standard SWH 150 liter including installation
- Cost of additional solar collector area, depending on the wall direction

Economic evaluation will result in the following economic parameters:

- $NPV > 0$
- $PV/I > 1.3$
- max SWH cost including installation for $PV/I=1.3$

Table 15 - City water temperature, °C

January	14.3
February	14.2
March	17.0
April	21.4
May	23.2
June	27.5
July	29.4
August	29.2
September	27.6
October	23.2
November	18.8
December	14.7

Analysis Options

- Option 1 - eleven accepted cases (out of 16) with increased solar collector size to supply the same amount of energy as the standard SWH with collectors at 45° tilt angle facing south.
- Option 2 – reduced area of the solar collectors on EES and SWW walls to avoid overheating above 77.3°C in August.
- Option 3 - all 16 cases of the building walls orientation, the size of solar collectors of the 11 cases of Option 2 remains as in Option 2, while the size of the solar collectors in all 5 cases not included in Option 2 is as in NNE-EES case of Option 2.

Option 1

Option 1 includes 11 accepted cases (out of 16) with increased solar collector size to supply the same amount of energy as standard SWH with collectors at 45° tilt angle facing south.

Table 16 - Solar radiation on wall, Set #12, Wh/day,m2

wall 1	NNE	NE	NEE	E	EES	ES	ESS	S	SSW	SW	SWW
wall 2	EES	ES	ESS	S	SSW	SW	SWW	W	WWN	WN	WNN
January	1978	2458	2893	3060	2879	2458	2893	3060	2879	2439	1954
February	2338	2723	3051	3193	3020	2723	3051	3193	3020	2667	2279
March	3035	3314	3519	3660	3584	3314	3519	3660	3584	3424	3142
April	3275	3272	3129	3015	3116	3272	3129	3015	3116	3233	3230
May	3633	3316	2830	2484	2771	3316	2830	2484	2771	3185	3437
June	3889	3359	2618	2178	2602	3359	2618	2178	2602	3267	3698
July	3536	3115	2514	2142	2548	3115	2514	2142	2548	3136	3500
August	3916	3695	3251	2916	3199	3695	3251	2916	3199	3572	3754
September	3702	3770	3641	3457	3376	3770	3641	3457	3376	3345	3199
October	3845	4318	4588	4564	4115	4318	4588	4564	4115	3632	3112
November	2946	3505	3856	3799	3292	3505	3856	3799	3292	2629	2058
December	2527	3190	3697	3778	3391	3190	3697	3778	3391	2686	2021

The data are related to the wall highlighted in yellow

Table 17 - Solar radiation on wall, Set #12, kcal/day,m2

wall 1	NNE	NE	NEE	E	EES	ES	ESS	S	SSW	SW	SWW
wall 2	EES	ES	ESS	S	SSW	SW	SWW	W	WWN	WN	WNN
January	1701	2114	2487	2631	2476	2114	2487	2631	2476	2097	1680
February	2010	2342	2624	2746	2597	2342	2624	2746	2597	2293	1960
March	2609	2850	3026	3147	3082	2850	3026	3147	3082	2944	2702
April	2816	2813	2691	2593	2679	2813	2691	2593	2679	2780	2777
May	3124	2851	2433	2136	2382	2851	2433	2136	2382	2739	2955
June	3344	2888	2251	1873	2237	2888	2251	1873	2237	2809	3179
July	3040	2679	2161	1842	2191	2679	2161	1842	2191	2696	3009
August	3367	3177	2795	2507	2751	3177	2795	2507	2751	3071	3228
September	3184	3242	3130	2973	2903	3242	3130	2973	2903	2876	2750
October	3306	3713	3945	3924	3538	3713	3945	3924	3538	3123	2676
November	2533	3014	3315	3267	2831	3014	3315	3267	2831	2261	1770
December	2173	2743	3179	3248	2916	2743	3179	3248	2916	2309	1737

The data are related to the wall highlighted in yellow

Option 1 - Solar Collectors Area

Table 18 - Option 1 – solar collectors size

wall 1	NNE	NE	NEE	E	EES	ES	ESS	S	SSW	SW	SWW
wall 2	EES	ES	ESS	S	SSW	SW	SWW	W	WWN	WN	WNN
SE on wall in Jan, kcal/day,m2	1701	2114	2487	2631	2476	2114	2487	2631	2476	2097	1680
required collector size, kcal/d	11946	9612	8168	7722	8206	9612	8168	7722	8206	9689	12095
additional collector area, kcal/d	4941	2607	1163	717	1201	2607	1163	717	1201	2684	5090
additional collector area, %	71%	37%	17%	10%	17%	37%	17%	10%	17%	38%	73%
additional collector area, m2	1.80	0.95	0.42	0.26	0.44	0.95	0.42	0.26	0.44	0.98	1.85
cost of additional collector area, \$	478	252	112	69	116	252	112	69	116	260	492

The data are related to the wall highlighted in yellow

Hot water temperature in the storage tank was calculated using Formula 2.

Table 19 - Option 1- hot water temperature in storage tank, °C

wall 1	NNE	NE	NEE	E	EES	ES	ESS	S	SSW	SW	SWW
wall 2	EES	ES	ESS	S	SSW	SW	SWW	W	WWN	WN	WNN
January	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45
February	51	48	47	46	46	48	47	46	46	48	50
March	64	59	54	54	55	59	54	54	55	60	67
April	72	62	55	52	55	62	55	52	55	62	72
May	80	65	53	48	53	65	53	48	53	63	77
June	88	70	55	49	55	70	55	49	55	69	86
July	84	68	56	51	57	68	56	51	57	69	85
August	90	75	64	59	63	75	64	59	63	74	88
September	85	75	66	62	64	75	66	62	64	70	78
October	83	77	72	69	67	77	72	69	67	69	72
November	65	63	60	57	54	63	60	57	54	52	51
December	54	55	54	53	51	55	54	53	51	49	47

The data are related to the wall highlighted in yellow

The oversized solar collectors on EES and SWW walls cause overheating above 80°C in summer. Therefore, Option 1 was disqualified.

Option 2

Option 2 includes 11 accepted cases (out of 16) with increased solar collector size to supply the same amount of energy as standard SWH with collectors at 45° tilt angle facing south.

In Option 2, the area of the solar collectors on EES and SWW walls was reduced to avoid overheating above 77.3°C in August.

However, the reduced solar collector will not supply the hot water at the required temperature in winter, which will increase electricity consumption for backup.

Option 2 - Solar Collectors Area

In Option 1, the oversized solar collectors show overheating above 80°C in summer on EES and SWW walls.

The maximum water temperature in the storage tank in all other cases is 77.3 °C.

Table 20 - Option 2 - reduced area of solar collectors on EES and SWW walls

wall		EES	SWW
month of max temperature		Aug	Aug
city water temperature	°C	29.2	29.2
Option 1 max temperature	°C	90.1	88.3
Option 1 Δt	°C	60.9	59.2
Option 2 max temperature	°C	77.3	77.3
Option 2 Δt	°C	48.1	48.1
collector size reduction		-21%	-19%
Option 1 collector area	m2	4.35	4.40
Option 2 collector area	m2	3.43	3.58

Hot water temperature in the storage tank was calculated using Formula 2.

Table 21 - Option 2 - hot water temperature in storage tank, °C

wall 1	NNE	NE	NEE	E	EES	ES	ESS	S	SSW	SW	SWW
wall 2	EES	ES	ESS	S	SSW	SW	SWW	W	WWN	WN	WNN
January	39	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	39
February	43	48	47	46	46	48	47	46	46	48	43
March	54	59	54	54	55	59	54	54	55	60	57
April	62	62	55	52	55	62	55	52	55	62	63
May	68	65	53	48	53	65	53	48	53	63	67
June	75	70	55	49	55	70	55	49	55	69	75
July	73	68	56	51	57	68	56	51	57	69	74
August	77	75	64	59	63	75	64	59	63	74	77
September	73	75	66	62	64	75	66	62	64	70	69
October	70	77	72	69	67	77	72	69	67	69	63
November	55	63	60	57	54	63	60	57	54	52	45
December	46	55	54	53	51	55	54	53	51	49	41

The data are related to the wall highlighted in yellow

Since the hot water temperature in the storage tank in EES and SWW cases is below the minimum 45°C in January, February and December, the electric backup will be increased in the relevant months.

Table 22 - Option 2 - additional backup for EES and SWW cases

		EES	SWW
required storage tank temperature	°C	45.1	45.1
collector size change		-21%	-19%
storage tank volume	liter	150	150
storage tank temperature in January	°C	38.6	39.3
Δt January	°C	6.5	5.8
additional backup in January	kWh/m	35.1	31.1
storage tank temperature in February	°C	42.9	43.4
Δt February	°C	2.2	1.7
additional backup in February	kWh/m	10.6	8.2
storage tank temperature in December	°C	N/A	40.6
Δt December	°C	0.0	4.5
additional backup in December	kWh/m	0.0	24.3
total additional backup	kWh/y	45.7	63.7
electricity tariffs	\$/kWh	0.21	0.21
total additional backup	\$/y	9.53	13.27

In EES and SWW cases the electric backup is higher than in all 9 other accepted cases. The electricity consumption for the additional backup will be included in the economic evaluation.

Table 23 - Option 2 – economic evaluation

wall 1	NNE	NE	NEE	E	EES	ES	ESS	S	SSW	SW	SWW
wall 2	EES	ES	ESS	S	SSW	SW	SWW	W	WWN	WN	WNN
additional collector area, m2	0.88	0.95	0.42	0.26	0.44	0.95	0.42	0.26	0.44	0.98	1.03
additional collector cost, \$	234	252	112	69	116	252	112	69	116	260	273
net investment, \$	691	709	569	526	573	709	569	526	573	716	730
electricity saving of standard SWH, \$/y	317	317	317	317	317	317	317	317	317	317	317
additional backup, \$/y	10										13
electricity saving, \$/y	307	317	317	317	317	317	317	317	317	317	304
PV = Saving/CRF [\$]	3,524	3,634	3,634	3,634	3,634	3,634	3,634	3,634	3,634	3,634	3,482
NPV, \$	2,834	2,925	3,064	3,108	3,061	2,925	3,064	3,108	3,061	2,917	2,751
PV/I	5.10	5.13	6.38	6.91	6.34	5.13	6.38	6.91	6.34	5.07	4.77
max SWH cost for PV/I=1.3 [\$]	3,777	3,861	3,861	3,861	3,861	3,861	3,861	3,861	3,861	3,861	3,744

The data are related to the wall highlighted in yellow

Option 3

Option 3 includes all 16 cases of the building walls' orientation. The size of solar collectors in the 11 cases of Option 2 remains as in Option 2, while the size of the solar collectors in all 5 cases not included in Option 2 is as the size on wall NNE-EES in Option 2.

The reason for not implementing the size of the SWW-WNN collector, which was the largest collector in Option 2, is overheating in the summer.

Table 24 - Option 3 – solar radiation on walls, kcal/day,m2

	N	NNE	NE	NEE	E	EES	ES	ESS	S	SSW	SW	SWW	W	WWN	WN	WNN
	E	EES	ES	ESS	S	SSW	SW	SSW	W	WWN	WN	WNN	N	NNE	NE	NEE
1	1299	1701	2114	2487	2631	2476	2114	2487	2631	2476	2097	1680	1284	935	719	943
2	1644	2010	2342	2624	2746	2597	2342	2624	2746	2597	2293	1960	1609	1276	1023	1292
3	2288	2609	2850	3026	3147	3082	2850	3026	3147	3082	2944	2702	2340	1906	1519	1903
4	2662	2816	2813	2691	2593	2679	2813	2691	2593	2679	2780	2777	2610	2315	1980	2372
5	3155	3124	2851	2433	2136	2382	2851	2433	2136	2382	2739	2955	2968	2792	2578	2969
6	3507	3344	2888	2251	1873	2237	2888	2251	1873	2237	2809	3179	3316	3178	2964	3366
7	3144	3040	2679	2161	1842	2191	2679	2161	1842	2191	2696	3009	3107	2937	2594	2974
8	3302	3367	3177	2795	2507	2751	3177	2795	2507	2751	3071	3228	3147	2834	2460	2981
9	2905	3184	3242	3130	2973	2903	3242	3130	2973	2903	2876	2750	2469	2077	1885	2450
10	2747	3306	3713	3945	3924	3538	3713	3945	3924	3538	3123	2676	2172	1663	1475	2095
11	1952	2533	3014	3315	3267	2831	3014	3315	3267	2831	2261	1770	1319	974	909	1380
12	1568	2173	2743	3179	3248	2916	2743	3179	3248	2916	2309	1737	1224	844	683	1044

The data are related to the wall highlighted in yellow

Table 25 - Option 3 – Solar collector size

	N	NNE	NE	NEE	E	EES	ES	ESS	S	SSW	SW	SWW	W	WWN	WN	WNN
	E	EES	ES	ESS	S	SSW	SW	SSW	W	WWN	WN	WNN	N	NNE	NE	NEE
collector size, m2	3.43	3.43	3.50	2.97	2.81	2.99	3.50	2.97	2.81	2.99	3.53	3.58	3.43	3.43	3.43	3.43
additional collector area, m2	0.88	0.88	0.95	0.42	0.26	0.44	0.95	0.42	0.26	0.44	0.98	1.03	0.88	0.88	0.88	0.88
additional collector cost, \$	234	234	252	112	69	116	252	112	69	116	260	273	234	234	234	234

The data are related to the wall highlighted in yellow

Table 26 - Option 3 - hot water temperature in storage tank, °C

	N	NNE	NE	NEE	E	EES	ES	ESS	S	SSW	SW	SWW	W	WWN	WN	WNN
	E	EES	ES	ESS	S	SSW	SW	SSW	W	WWN	WN	WNN	N	NNE	NE	NEE
1	33	39	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	39	33	28	25	28	
2	38	43	48	47	46	46	48	47	46	46	43	37	32	29	33	
3	50	54	59	54	54	55	59	54	54	55	60	57	50	44	39	44
4	59	62	62	55	52	55	62	55	52	55	62	63	59	54	50	55
5	68	68	65	53	48	53	65	53	48	53	63	67	66	63	60	66
6	78	75	70	55	49	55	70	55	49	55	69	75	75	73	70	76
7	74	73	68	56	51	57	68	56	51	57	69	74	74	71	66	72
8	76	77	75	64	59	63	75	64	59	63	74	77	74	70	64	72
9	69	73	75	66	62	64	75	66	62	64	70	69	63	57	54	63
10	62	70	77	72	69	67	77	72	69	67	69	63	54	47	44	53
11	47	55	63	60	57	64	63	60	57	64	52	45	38	33	32	39
12	37	46	55	54	53	51	55	54	53	51	49	41	32	27	24	30

The data are related to the wall highlighted in yellow

The maximum water temperature in Option 3 is 77.6°C on wall N-E in June.

The minimum water temperature without backup in Option 3 is 24.4°C on wall WN-NE in December.

In cases when the water temperature is below 45.1°C, additional backup will be needed. The electricity consumption for the additional backup will be included in the economic evaluation.

Table 27 - Option 3 – additional backup, kWh/month

	N	NNE	NE	NEE	E	EES	ES	ESS	S	SSW	SW	SWW	W	WWN	WN	WNN	
	E	EES	ES	ESS	S	SSW	SW	SWW	W	WWN	WN	WNN	N	NNE	NE	NEE	
1	66	35											31	67	94	111	94
2	36	11											8	39	62	79	61
3															4	34	5
4																	
5																	
6																	
7																	
8																	
9																	
10																4	
11													39	65	70	34	
12	43												24	70	99	111	84
kWh/y	145	46	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	64	215	324	410	277

The data are related to the wall highlighted in yellow

Table 28 - Option 3 – economic evaluation

	N	NNE	NE	NEE	E	EES	ES	ESS	S	SSW	SW	SWW	W	WWN	WN	WNN
	E	EES	ES	ESS	S	SSW	SW	SWW	W	WWN	WN	WNN	N	NNE	NE	NEE
additional collector area, m2	0.88	0.88	0.95	0.42	0.26	0.44	0.95	0.42	0.26	0.44	0.98	1.03	0.88	0.88	0.88	0.88
additional collector cost, \$	234	234	252	112	69	116	252	112	69	116	260	273	234	234	234	234
net investment, \$	691	691	709	569	526	573	709	569	526	573	716	730	691	691	691	691
additional backup, kWh/y	145	46	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	64	215	324	410
electricity saving, kWh/y	1375	1474	1520	1520	1520	1520	1520	1520	1520	1520	1520	1520	1456	1305	1196	1110
electricity saving of standard SWH, \$/y	317	317	317	317	317	317	317	317	317	317	317	317	317	317	317	317
additional backup, \$/y	30	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	13	45	68	85
electricity saving, \$/y	286	307	317	317	317	317	317	317	317	317	317	317	304	272	249	259
PV = Saving/CRF [\$]	3286	3524	3634	3634	3634	3634	3634	3634	3634	3634	3634	3634	3482	3121	2859	2654
NPV, \$	2595	2834	2925	3064	3108	3061	2925	3064	3108	3061	2917	2751	2430	2168	1963	2281
PV/I	4.76	5.10	5.13	6.38	6.91	6.34	5.13	6.38	6.91	6.34	5.07	4.77	4.52	4.14	3.84	4.30
max SWH cost for PV/I=1.3 [\$]	3594	3777	3861	3861	3861	3861	3861	3861	3861	3861	3861	3861	3744	3467	3265	3107

The data are related to the wall highlighted in yellow

Table 29 - Option 3 – averages

		Ave	Max	Min	
collector size	m2	3.26	3.58	SWW+WNN	2.81 South
electricity saving	kWh/y	1,427	1,520	9 cases	1,110 WN+NE
NPV	\$	2,766	3,108	South	1,963 WN+NE
PV/I		5.38	6.91	South	3.84 WN+NE

Sensitivity Analysis

The sensitivity analysis will be done for one parameter only – life expectancy, which will be reduced from 20 years to 8 years.

Table 30 - Option 3 – sensitivity analysis – life expectancy 8 years instead of 20

life expectancy	years	20	8
Rate of Interest	%/y	6%	6%
CRF [10]		0.0872	0.1610

Table 31 - Option 3 – sensitivity analysis – life expectancy 8 years instead of 20

	N	NNE	NE	NEE	E	EES	ES	ESS	S	SSW	SW	SWW	W	WWN	WN	WNN
	E	EES	ES	ESS	S	SSW	SW	SWW	W	WWN	WN	WNN	N	NNE	NE	NEE
PV, \$	1779	1908	1967	1967	1967	1967	1967	1967	1967	1967	1967	1885	1690	1548	1437	1609
NPV, \$	1088	1217	1258	1398	1441	1394	1258	1398	1441	1394	1251	1155	999	857	746	918
PV/I	2.58	2.76	2.77	3.46	3.74	3.43	2.77	3.46	3.74	3.43	2.75	2.58	2.45	2.24	2.08	2.33

The data are related to the wall highlighted in yellow

Table 32 - Option 3 – sensitivity analysis – life expectancy 20 years and 8 years

Life expectancy		20 years	8 years
NPV Ave	\$	2,766	1,201
NPV Max	\$	3,108	1,441
NPV Min	\$	1,963	746
PV/I Ave		5.38	2.91
PV/I Max		6.91	3.74
PV/I Min		3.84	2.08

The sensitivity analysis shows that even after reducing the SWH life expectancy from 20 years to 8 years, all cases remain highly profitable with an average PV/I of 2.91 and a minimum of 2.08.

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